

Molar volume, viscosity and conductance studies of copper sulphate in some multicomponent solutions (CuSO₄·5H₂O-dextrose-NaCl-H₂O)

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Abstract : Molar volume, viscosity and molar conductance of copper sulphate in water, 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride and 5–15 wt% dextrose in 0.1 M sodium chloride solutions have been evaluated from density, viscosity and conductance data respectively at temperature 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. The strong solute-solvent interactions for copper sulphate in various compositions of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride have been inferred from ϕ_v^0 , B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation and Λ^0 values. The structure making/breaking behaviour of copper sulphate from molar volume data has been inferred from the sign of $[\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_P$ and it has been found that copper sulphate behaves as structure breaker. The positive B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation have been obtained from viscosity data which is due to structure breaking behaviour of copper sulphate in water and 5–15 wt% dextrose in 0.1 M NaCl solutions. The structure breaking behaviour of copper sulphate has also been obtained from Walden product studies.

Keywords : Molar volume, viscosity, conductance, multicomponent systems.

The study of apparent molar volumes of electrolytes at infinite dilution, B parameter of Jones-Dole equation and their dependence on temperature, molar conductance at infinite dilution and Walden product studies can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions. The behaviour of electrolytes in aqueous carbohydrates and aqueous carbohydrates containing small quantity of ions which are present in body fluids have recently been subject of interest¹. Increasing concern over the toxicity of heavy metals in the environment has led to increase in research activity to identify the fate of these metal ions in the organisms. The large amount of copper is toxic and thus copper salts may act as insecticides and fungicides. The small amount of copper is essential to life and adult contains about 100 mg. This is the third largest amount after Fe (4 g) and Zn (2 g). There is a need of 4–5 mg of copper daily in the diet, and deficiency in animal results in the inability to use iron stored in the liver and thus animals suffer from an anemia. The copper is bound to proteins in the body either as metalloproteins or as enzymes. The study of copper sulphate in 5–15 wt% dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K temperatures was carried out to understand the nature of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions by measuring the density, molar volume, molar conductance and viscosity of their solutions.

Experimental

Water used for solutions had specific conductance in the range 0.1–1.0 $\times 10^{-6}$ Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹. Copper sulphate, sodium chloride and dextrose (AnalaR) were dried over anhydrous calcium chloride for more than 48 h and used as such. All the solutions were prepared by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was done by using the standard expression². The concentration range of CuSO₄·5H₂O in 5–15 wt.% dextrose 0.1 M NaCl solution was 0.01 to 0.1 M. The density was measured with the help of a double capillary pycnometer (25 ml capacity) as described elsewhere³. The pycnometer was calibrated with conductivity water and values of carbon tetrachloride and chloroform were measured as : 1.58377 \pm 0.00025 and 1.47048 \pm 0.00026 g ml⁻¹ respectively. Their values are comparable with the literature values⁴. Viscosity was determined with the help of capillary type viscometer⁵. The conductance was measured by methods described earlier⁶. All measurements were made in a water bath maintained at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C (\pm 0.05 °C).

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volume of copper sulphate in 5, 10 and 15 wt.% dextrose + 0.1 M NaCl in water solutions have been calculated from density data by using eq. (1)

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d^0} - \frac{1000(d - d^0)}{md^0} \quad (1)$$

where d^o is the density of solvent, d the density of solution, m the molality of solution and M_2 the molecular weight of the copper sulphate. Errors in ϕ_v were calculated from eq. (2)

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2) (1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) assumes error to be associated with the density of solution (d) and solvent (d^o). Moreover, errors associated with determination of solution concentration are not the limiting factor while calculating the apparent molar volumes. The error in apparent molar volume as derived from eq. (2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01 M concentration to $\pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.10 M concentration. The densities of various solutions of copper sulphate in 5, 10 and 15 percent dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride obey Root's equation and justify the use of Masson's eq. (3) for the estimation of the limiting apparent molar volume.

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^o + S_v \sqrt{c} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v^o and S_v are calculated from the intercept and slope from the extrapolation of the plots of ϕ_v versus \sqrt{c} . The values of limiting molar volume and slopes S_v are recorded in Table 1. The slope S_v in Masson's equation may be attributed to be as a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interactions⁷, low and positive values accounts for low solute-solute interactions for copper sulphate in 5–15

wt. % of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride solutions. There is decrease in inter ionic interactions with increase of temperature for all concentrations of dextrose. This may be due to the decrease in molecular interactions in the solvent system due to decrease in hydrogen bonding between solvent molecules with increase in temperature. Due to this reason more free solvent molecules will be available for metal ions for solvation with increase in temperature.

The ϕ_v^o is a measure of solute-solvent interactions⁸.

The limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^o values of copper sulphate are positive and high in 0, 5, 10 and 15% dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride solutions at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K temperature show more solute-solvent interactions. The solute-solvent interactions for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ increase with increase in concentration of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride and it also increases with increase in temperature in all concentrations of dextrose. The increase in solute-solvent interactions with increase in concentration of dextrose and with increase in temperature may be due to increase in solvation of metal ions.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^o for copper sulphate in water and 0, 5, 10 and 15 wt% dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride can be expressed as :

Table 1. Limiting apparent molar volume ϕ_v^o , S_v , apparent molar expansibility (ϕ_E^o) and excess molar volume ($\Delta\phi_v^o$) of copper sulphate in different compositions of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride at different temperatures

Dextrose Wt. %	Temp. (T) (K)	ϕ_v^o ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	S_v ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ l}^{1/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$)	ϕ_E^o ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$\Delta\phi_v^o = (\Delta\phi_v^o, \text{CuSO}_4 \text{ in dextrose} + \text{aq. NaCl} - \phi_v^o, \text{CuSO}_4 \text{ in aq. NaCl})$
0	303.0	72.9	2.417	5.125	-
0	308.0	95.4	1.154	3.886	-
0	313.0	110.9	0.968	2.648	-
0	318.0	121.1	0.596	1.408	-
5.00	303.0	78.6	0.467	6.696	5.74
5.00	308.0	106.2	0.452	4.324	10.76
5.00	313.0	137.9	0.222	1.950	26.90
5.00	318.0	141.7	0.359	-0.422	20.58
10.00	303.0	125.4	0.772	0.988	52.44
10.00	308.0	129.5	0.656	0.660	34.04
10.00	313.0	142.5	0.224	0.330	31.48
10.00	318.0	143.3	0.099	-0.002	22.17
15.00	303.0	150.3	0.690	5.916	77.41
15.00	308.0	174.9	0.630	3.936	79.51
15.00	313.0	178.9	0.383	1.954	67.94
15.00	318.0	182.9	0.328	-0.026	61.80

$$\varphi_v^0 = -192.37 + 12.56t - 0.124t^2 \quad (4)$$

= (CuSO₄.5H₂O in 0.1 M aq. NaCl)

$$\varphi_v^0 = -272.82 + 17.03t - 0.177t^2 \quad (5)$$

= (CuSO₄.5H₂O in 5 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl)

$$\varphi_v^0 = 66.095 + 2.96t - 0.033t^2 \quad (6)$$

= (CuSO₄.5H₂O in 10 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl)

$$\varphi_v^0 = -205.46 + 17.80t - 0.198t^2 \quad (7)$$

= (CuSO₄.5H₂O in 15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl)

where t is the temperature in degree celsius.

The limiting apparent molar expansibility $\varphi_E^0 = (\partial\varphi_v^0/\partial T^2)$ calculated for copper sulphate from eqs. (4), (5), (6) and (7) decrease with increase in temperature (Table 1) shows the absence of caging effect. The structure making/breaking capacity of copper sulphate may be interpreted with the help of Hepler's reasoning, i.e. on the basis of sign $(\partial^2\varphi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p$. It has been shown from general thermodynamic eq. (8)

$$(\partial\bar{C}_p^0/\partial p)_T = -T(\partial^2\varphi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p \quad (8)$$

where \bar{C}_p^0 is the partial molar heat capacity at infinite dilution. From eq. (8) it is clear that a structure making solute should have a positive value of $(\partial^2\varphi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p$. For copper sulphate in 0, 5, 10 and 15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl solution $(\partial^2\varphi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p$ has been found negative and hence copper sulphate acts as structure breaker in 0.1 M aq. NaCl and 5-15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl solutions.

The limiting excess molar volume of copper sulphate for different compositions of dextrose have been estimated from eq. (9)

$$\Delta\varphi_v^0(\text{excess}) = \varphi_v^0(A) - \varphi_v^0(B) \quad (9)$$

where $\varphi_v^0(A)$ is the limiting apparent molar volume of copper sulphate in various composition of dextrose in 0.1 M NaCl solution and $\varphi_v^0(B)$ is the limiting apparent molar volume of copper sulphate in 0.1 M aq. sodium chloride. The positive values of $\varphi_v^0(\text{excess})$, suggest solvation of metal ions. The increase in the values of $\Delta\varphi_v^0(\text{excess})$ with increase in concentration of dextrose suggests increase in solute-solvent interactions for copper sulphate with increase in composition of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride. The effect of the temperature show that $\Delta\varphi_v^0(\text{excess})$ first increases with increase in temperature, reaches maximum and then decreases with further increase of temperature. This data show that solvation of

metal ions first increases with increase of temperature, reaches maximum and then decreases which may be explained due to decrease of hydrogen bonding between solvent molecules at high temperature and due to establishment of ionic equilibrium in the solvent system at high temperature.

Viscosity studies :

The viscosity data has been analyzed on the basis of Jones-Dole equation⁹.

$$\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + BC \quad (10)$$

where η_s and η_0 are viscosities of solution and solvent respectively, c is the molar concentration and A and B are constants. The values of A and B have been determine from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $\eta_s/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{c}$ versus \sqrt{c} . The values of A and B of different solutions are recorded in Table 2.

Parameter A of Jones-Dole equation represents the contribution from solute-solute interactions¹⁰. The positive A value for copper sulphate in 5-15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous NaCl at temp. 303, 308, 313 and 318 K are due to strong ion-ion interactions. The A values decrease with increase in concentration of dextrose and with increase in temperature which may be due to increase in solvation of metal ions with increase in concentration of dextrose as well as increase in temperature of the system. The B parameter which measures the structure making/breaking capacity of an electrolyte in a solution also contains a contribution from structural effects and is responsible for solute-solvent interaction in a solvent¹¹. It has been emphasized by a number of workers that dB/dT is more important criteria¹² for determining solute-solvent interaction, as positive B -coefficient obtained from aqueous dextrose solution in 0.1 M NaCl can be interpreted as may be due to large size ion. Viscosity study of number of electrolytes has shown that structure-breaker will have positive dB/dT . The temperature effect on copper sulphate in 0, 5, 10 and 15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl shows a positive sign of dB/dT , showing there by that copper sulphate behaves as a structure breaker.

Conductance studies :

The limiting molar conductance Λ_m^0 for copper sulphate in different compositions of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride were obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of Λ_m versus \sqrt{c} to zero concentration. The limiting molar conductance of copper sulphate in 0.1 M aq. NaCl and 5, 10 and 15 wt.% dextrose in 0.1 M aq. NaCl solutions at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K are recorded

Table 2. Values of parameters of Jone-Dole equation, limiting molar conductance, Λ_m^0 and Walden product for copper sulphate in different compositions of dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous NaCl at different temperatures

Dextrose Wt. %	Temp. (T) (K)	A (l mol ⁻¹) ^{1/2}	B (l mol ⁻¹)	Λ_m^0 (Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹)	($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) (Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹ poise)
0	303	26.06	0.770	169.3	1.26
0	308	23.66	0.865	191.4	1.19
0	313	19.89	0.060	197.8	1.25
0	318	11.85	1.305	242.7	0.85
5	303	21.32	0.684	161.0	1.44
5	308	21.02	0.873	173.2	1.53
5	313	11.36	1.406	184.4	1.51
5	318	3.28	1.685	186.6	1.33
10	303	15.96	0.981	156.3	1.59
10	308	9.57	1.392	159.3	1.59
10	313	6.24	1.546	172.7	1.56
10	318	3.08	1.727	176.3	1.42
15	303	10.52	1.234	149.7	1.82
15	308	9.06	1.323	150.8	1.75
15	313	3.43	1.582	152.6	1.57
15	318	2.37	1.677	164.0	1.47

in Table 2 show that the limiting molar conductance increase with rise in temperature, which may be due to increase in ionic mobility of free Cu^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , Na^+ and Cl^- ions at infinite dilution. The Λ_m^0 values of CuSO_4 decrease with increase in concentration of carbohydrate (i.e. dextrose). It may be due to increase in solvation of metal ions and increase in association of CuSO_4 with increase in carbohydrate contents.

The Λ_m^0 has been regarded as a measure of solute-solvent interaction¹³, greater the magnitude of Λ_m^0 , greater the solute-solvent interaction. The high and positive values of limiting molar conductance of CuSO_4 in 5–15 wt. % dextrose in 0.1 M aqueous NaCl suggest more solute-solvent interactions at all temperatures 303–308 K. The Λ_m^0 values show that solute-solvent interactions of CuSO_4 is more in aqueous NaCl than in 5–15 wt. % dextrose.

The Walden product data ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) have been recorded in Table 2 increases with increase in percentage of dextrose showing decrease in solute-solvent interactions with increase in the content of carbohydrate. From Walden product studies for CuSO_4 in 5, 10 and 15% dextrose at different temperatures, solute-solvent interactions increases with increase of temperature.

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